

Nangai Puthi Aditha Pidariyar

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Abstract

In medieval Tamil country, Chola temples had borne the names of the Chola rulers, queens and princess. The Chola queens had involved in the cultural arena which was so great that their names will forever be remembered in this regard. Chola queens Sembayan Madevi, Kundavai Pirattiyar, Lokhamadevi and Panchavan madevi were actively participated in the temples services. Among the Chola queens, Pudi Aditha Pidari who constructed Shiva temple at Triuchchendurai near Thiruchirapalli. She made numerous endowments to the temple.

Keywords: Temples, Inscriptions, Endowments

Introduction

The Chola Empire was one of India's great empires in medieval Tamilnadu, and the art and architecture writing from that period is utterly gorgeous. There are considerable number of evidences available for a study of royal women in the Chola dynasty. Numerous endowments has been granted to the temples for various purposes and that was recorded in epigraphs. The queens had great interest in the propagation of religion, particularly saivism. Puthi Aditha Pidari had constructed the Karrali Perumanadikal temple and made numerous endowments to the temple. Pudhi Aditha Pidari was a forerunner of later queens for the temple building activities.

Puthi Aditha Pidari was the daughter of Kodumbalur chief, named Puthi Vikrama Kesari alias Thennavan Ilankovel and wife of Arikulakesari. Puthi Aditha Pidari built the Siva temple at Thiruchendurai near Tiruchy. Thiruchendurai temple has been converted into stone even before Parantaka I in the days of Aditya I. Because he had converted 108 Siva temples on both the banks of river Kaveri into stone. This temple also might be one among them not only that intersetingly the presiding god of this temple is named as Karrali Paramesvarar. An inscription of 23r year of Rajakesarivarman which mentions Nangai Aditha Pidari who figures almost continuously upto 14th year of Parantaka I, mention of this stone temple which has to be identified the temple with stone by Nangai Aditha Pidariyar. She had donated liberally for the well being of this temple which is attested by a number of inscriptions found in this temple.

Endowments of Nangai Puthi Aditha Pidari

Puthi Aditha Pidari has purchased two veli extent of land from Esanamangalam village and endowed to this temple through his father Sembiyan Ilangovel alias Puthi Aditha Pidan. The inscription makes provision for sacred offerings to the god from the interest on the endowment of 60 kalanju of gold. Aditha Pidari has purchased quarter cey extent of land from one musician Saththan Senthan who got this land as a sridhana. In this same temple Nakkan Vikkiramakesari, the wife of Thennavan Ilangovel alias Puthi Vikkiramakesari endowed 20 kalanju measure of gold with the Mulaparishath sabha, the administrative body for burning one perpetual lamp. One more record registers a sale of land to Nangai Puthi Aditha Pidari by the Mulaparishath of this temple at the value of seven and a half kalanju gold. This land might have been donated by her to this temple for some other purpose. But that detail is not clear in this record.

Puthi Aditha Pidari had endowed 10 kalanju of gold with the Mulaparishath of this temple. They ensured to pay the taxes due interest and protect this gold as capital amount forever in this temple. During the fourth regnal year of Parakesari, queen Puthi Athitha Pidari purchased one garden at a extent of 2000 paththi and against this, she paid (37 ½) thirty seven and half kalanju of gold to the Mulaparishath the administrative body. This body assured to pay regularly the tax due for the garden to the temple.

Puthi Athitha Pidari has endowed 28 ¼ kalanj of gold to this temple of Thiruchendurai Mahadeva. The brahmadeya officials purchased one and half cey for this amount and assured to pay the due taxes to the temple of Thiruchendurai Mahadeva.

She purchased one garden land from a potter, another garden from the ur and one garden was given to the sabha. All these lands were donated by her for making flower garden and for the construction of residential quarters for the tillers of the temple land. During the twenty third regnal year of the Sundarachola the Mulaparishath of Eranamangalam had sold some lands to Puthi Aditha Pidari 5 kalanju of gold. The land was measured as 6 Ma extent and it was donated by Puthi Aditha Pidari for the uvachchas (for Drumming service) of this temple.

During the third regnal year of king Parakesari (may be Parantaka I 910CE) this Puthi Aditha Pidari donated 60 kalanju gold to the Karrali Peruman Adigal temple which was constructed by herself. The Mulaparishath of this temple accepted this 60 kalanju of gold for the daily food. Mulaparishath has extracted sixty kalam pady as interest for the 60 kalanju of gold. This donation was carried on till the sun and the moon exist. Puthi Aditha Pidari had also donated some garden lands for the festivals to celebrate on the solar eclipse days in the Karraliperumanadigal temple. This donation was made by her during the second regnal year of the king Uttamacholaparakesari. For this endowment Pudhi Aditha Pidari had purchased the garden lands from two Brahmins namely Kasyapan Rathanarayanan and Parathayan Isanamaran.

Food Offerings

An inscription of Parantakan I registers, about endowment of Nangai Puthi Aditha Pidari I kuruni rice pound 10 or 8 times for sacred offerings in the midday to the Thiruchendurai Mahadeva temple. She purchased two gardens and endowed them as Tiruvilapuram to meet out the expenses for the festivals on the day of Solar eclipse. In 30th regnal year of Parantakan I speaks about the endowment of Puthi Aditha Pidari, every month on the day of his natal star Poorattadi to perform sacred bath on ghee, and food offerings were rice, neiyamudu, banana, porikari, ilayamirthu and adaikkai amirdu to the temple. Aditha Pidari made various food offerings to Karrali Mahadevar at Thiruchchendurai, appam for Ganapathi and Thiruvamudu, paruppu neiyamudu and thayiramudu.

Arinjigai Pirattiyar has donated 15 kalanju gold to meet out the expenses of certain festival and a special food offering during the days of 14th year of Rajaraja Chola in the Thirunagesvaram

temple. she also endowed 37 ½ kalanju of gold for the mid-night puja at the same temple at Thirunagesvaram. On the east wall of the Sakkattan Mandapa in front of the Panchanadesvara temple at Thiruvaiyaru we have an inscription of Kulottungachola dated in the 40th year mentions a gift of land for feeding a Brahman with sumptuous meal daily by queen Arinjigai.

Conclusion

Most of the Chola queens were active in the religious and cultural spheres and their names are remembered even today in history. The Thiruchchendurai temple also helps us to understand the strong relationship between Cholas and Velirs. The temple is also one of the fine example of early Chola temple architecture. Puthi Aditha Pidari's temple still shines a light on hitherto unexpected facets of Indian society of the past. Puthi Aditha Pidari as a philanthropist, not only constructed the temple but also endowed the temples with offerings. She was an inspiration of other Chola queens and she made a historical awareness.

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